

1 **BLAST VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT OF ROAD TUNNELS WITH REINFORCED**
2 **CONCRETE LINERS**

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15 **ABSTRACT**

16 Tunnels are a critical component of our transportation infrastructure, and unexpected damage to a
17 tunnel can significantly and adversely impact the functionality of a transportation network. Tunnel systems
18 are vulnerable to potential threats of intentional and accidental blast events due to their relatively
19 unrestricted public access. These events can lead to spalling and breach of the tunnel liner which, depending
20 on the surrounding media, can result in local damage and progressive collapse of the tunnel. Current
21 approaches for evaluating blast-induced damage to a tunnel liner either require significant computational
22 effort or oversimplification such that accurate spatial distributions of damage cannot be obtained. This study
23 presents an effective approach to predict and map the damage to a reinforced concrete liner of a roadway
24 tunnel from various explosive threat sizes and tunnel geometries. A literature review of existing studies is
25 conducted, and potential scenarios of blast events are examined with varying charge position and size.
26 Rectangular, horseshoe, and circular tunnel geometries, each with the same traffic throughput, are evaluated.
27 An efficient analytical approach to determine the spatial distribution of blast-induced spall and breach
28 damage is presented and shows good agreement with numerical models analyzed in LS-DYNA. The
29 proposed approach is then used to examine the relationship between increasing blast hazard intensity and
30 the extent of spall and breach damage. Inflection points in this relationship can be used to identify hazard
31 levels at which a progressive collapse evaluation would be warranted.

32
33 **Keywords:** Tunnels; blast; concrete liner; progressive collapse; breach; spalling
34

35 **INTRODUCTION**

36 Extreme threats such as blast, fire, and vehicle accidents pose challenges to the safety of
37 transportation infrastructure. The threats themselves can result in direct loss of life and can lead to localized
38 damage and catastrophic outcomes such as progressive collapse. Bridges and tunnels are typically
39 considered critical to our national infrastructure since the incapacity or damage of such structures would
40 jeopardize regional security as well as economic functionality. A Presidential Policy Directive (1) has
41 specifically stipulated the need to strengthen the security and resilience of our nation's critical infrastructure.
42 Furthermore, an NCHRP study of transportation tunnel security recently highlighted the threats posed by
43 intentional and accidental blast (2).

44 Roadway tunnels are particularly vulnerable to terrorist attack since most have uncontrolled public
45 access to vehicles ranging from motorbikes and passenger cars to large cargo-hauling trucks. Though the
46 risk of terrorist attack is low, consideration of these threats is amplified since (1) they typically carry high
47 consequence; (2) they are attracted to high-impact, high-visibility targets, particularly those with lower
48 levels of perceived security; and (3) public fear or dread of these events contributes to "probability neglect,"
49 which is the goal of most terrorist activities (3). Between 1970 and 2015, the United States alone has seen
50 89 terrorist attacks targeting the transportation sector, 64% of which were carried out through bombings (4).
51 Tunnels specifically may pose an even greater concern when considering the additional confinement during
52 a blast as well as the enclosed space in which to operate rescue and repair efforts. Though many recent
53 incidents around the world have involved hand-carried threats in subway tunnels (5), US government
54 agencies have been focusing their mitigation efforts more on the threat posed by vehicle-borne improvised
55 explosive devices (VBIEDs) (2).

56 The aforementioned NCHRP effort has highlighted a need for improved assessment of
57 transportation tunnel vulnerability to blast (2). In particular, few available approaches can provide
58 reasonably conservative, computationally efficient evaluations of the spatial distribution and structural
59 consequences of blast-induced damage. Numerous research studies have examined the propagation of blast-
60 induced pressure loads in tunnels and other confined structures via experiments (6, 7) and high-fidelity
61 computational fluid dynamic analysis (8-10). The results of these studies have made strides in establishing
62 the temporal and spatial distribution of blast pressure on tunnel liners. Some studies have used finite element
63 (FE) analyses to model the spalling and/or breach effects of these blast loads on the tunnel liners, which are
64 typically constructed of reinforced concrete (7, 11, 12). Previous studies have collectively demonstrated

65 that shock-induced cracking, spalling, and breach is the dominant failure mode of tunnel liners in response
66 to blast pressure, as opposed to the flexural response that are more typical of many building or bridge
67 structures.

68 The most significant contributions made by previous research in this field have typically pertained
69 to the use of high-fidelity modeling tools, which are computationally demanding and are not conducive to
70 parametric assessment of tunnels subjected to blast loads. This study addresses the need for assessment
71 tools of “intermediate” complexity, which can deliver accurate, conservative assessments of blast-induced
72 damage at a fraction of the computational effort of high-fidelity models. A similar approach to intermediate
73 models has been developed previously by one of the authors for the vulnerability of bridges to unconfined
74 hydrocarbon fires (13). This study will focus on the levels of spall and breach damage induced by VBIED
75 hazards that are traveling in typical roadway tunnels. Three tunnel prototypes with varying geometry but
76 identical vehicle throughput are evaluated for a range of blast hazards. Spatial contours of damage are
77 developed using the proposed approach and are compared to results obtained from high-fidelity
78 computational analysis.

79 The proposed approach can be used to efficiently establish the relationship between blast hazard
80 intensity and the extent of damage for a range of tunnel design parameters or conditions. The extent of
81 tunnel damage can then be used as the initial conditions for progressive collapse assessment of the tunnel
82 liner. A similar approach for mapping blast-induced damage as a prelude to progressive collapse evaluation
83 was used previously by the authors for building frame structures (14). The proposed approach is used to
84 develop threat vs. damage curves which indicate appropriate hazard levels for which progressive collapse
85 resistant design may be feasible and/or warranted. Increases in tunnel wall thickness as a function of tunnel
86 geometry are also developed to illustrate the relative amount of concrete needed to prevent blast-induced
87 breach of the tunnel liner.

88 **BLAST EVALUATION OF TUNNELS**

89 This study will focus on VBIED blast hazards and the associated spall and breach damage to the
90 liner of common reinforced concrete tunnels. Detonation of explosive materials generate a rapidly
91 expanding pressure wave that radiates spherically from the charge. These shock waves can generate a
92 significant pressure impulse when they impact structural components in their path. This short-duration load
93 is termed reflected pressure and varies in magnitude and duration depending on the size of explosive,
94 standoff distance, and the spatial orientation of the loaded component to the shock wave front. Blast
95 demands are generally divided into contact, close-in, and far-field events. Far-field events are generally
96 assumed to occur at a scaled distance of greater than $5.0 \text{ ft/lb}^{1/3}$, where scaled distance is the standoff
97 distance (in feet) divided by the cube root of the charge size (in lbs of TNT). Contact and close-in events
98 occur at smaller scaled distances. The response of a conventional reinforced concrete structural component
99 under a far-field blast demand is typically governed by flexural and shear response. Tunnel liners are
100 backed by the surrounding media and are thus resistant to flexural modes of damage. The response to a
101 close-in event is controlled by stress wave propagation through the thickness of the component, thereby
102 resulting in spalling, cracking, and breach. In tunnel liners under blast loading, the pressure demand
103 generates a compression wave through the thickness of the concrete liner that can cause spalling as the
104 compression wave reflects off the back and/or front surfaces, i.e. causing the stress to exceed the dynamic
105 strength capacity. If the depth of spall approaches the liner thickness, a breached opening can be generated
106 through the component. Tunnel liners may experience an even more pronounced spall and breach damage
107 response if the surrounding media has a higher impedance to the shockwave propagation. Tunnel enclosures
108 limit the available standoff and can result in reflection of the blast front such that each surface can
109 experience multiple pressure impulses. Therefore, the primary concern for tunnel liners subject to blast
110 loads is breach and spall damage.

111 Evaluations of the damage resulting from blast events have been conducted via either experimental
112 studies or complex numerical modelling. Full scale blast events are very expensive to conduct, and
113 alternative means (such as scaled tests via small charges, shock tubes, or impact hammers) are often used
114 for damage analysis. Experimental studies such as Colombo et al. (15) focused mainly on the development

115 of new tunnel liner technologies rather than the evaluation of existing inventories.

116 PROPOSED FRAMEWORK FOR BLAST DAMAGE ASSESSMENT

117 UFC 3-340-02, a US Government manual for blast resistant structural design (16), utilizes an
118 empirical approach for calculating spall and breach in concrete slabs due to blast loading as a function of
119 concrete compressive strength, as shown in Figure 1. The empirical equations (Eq. 1 and 2) are valid for a
120 wide range of data as shown in (16).

$$121 \quad \text{Spall Threshold: } \frac{h}{R} = \frac{1}{a + b\Psi^{2.5} + c\Psi^{0.5}} \quad (1)$$

$$122 \quad \text{Breach Threshold: } \frac{h}{R} = \frac{1}{a + b\Psi + c\Psi^2} \quad (2)$$

123 where h = concrete thickness (ft); R = standoff from slab face to charge center of gravity (ft); and Ψ = spall
124 parameter. In Eq. (1), $a = -0.02511$; $b = 0.01004$; $c = 0.13613$; in Eq. (2), $a = 0.028205$; $b = 0.144308$; $c =$
125 0.049265 . For the non-contact and contact charges, the spall parameter Ψ is calculated from Eq. 3 and 4,
126 respectively.

$$127 \quad \text{Non-Contact Charges: } \Psi = R^{0.926} f_c^{0.266} W_{adj}^{-0.353} (W_{adj} / (W_{adj} + W_c))^{0.333} \quad (3)$$

$$128 \quad \text{Contact Charges: } \Psi = 0.527 R^{0.972} f_c^{0.308} W_{adj}^{-0.341} \quad (4)$$

129 where f_c = concrete compressive strength (psi); W_c = steel casing weight (lb); W_{adj} = adjusted charge weight
130 (lb) = $B_f C_f W$; W = equivalent TNT charge weight (lb); B_f = burst configuration factor (1.0 for surface bursts,
131 0.5 for free air bursts); C_f = cylindrical charge factor, calculated in accordance with Eq. 5 and 6.

$$132 \quad \text{For } L > D \text{ and } R/W^{0.333} < 2.0, C_f = 1.0 \quad (5)$$

$$133 \quad \text{Else: } C_f = 1 + 2 \left(LD / \left(\pi (3LD^2 / 16)^{0.667} \right) - 1 \right) \left(1 - R / \left(2W^{0.333} \right) \right) \quad (6)$$

134 where L = charge length; D = charge diameter. Dynamic strength increases due to strain rate effects are
135 included in the expression of Ψ (16). As summarized in Table 1, the applicability of the model is limited to
136 the range of test data on which the equations were founded. In these equations, W_{adj} is the weight of a
137 hemispherical surface charge that applies an explosive impulse at the target equal to that of the actual charge.

138 In this study, breach and spall thresholds are applied to a tunnel geometry as spheres with radii
139 explicitly solved from Eq. (1). The intersection of these spheres with the tunnel liner denotes the extent of
140 breach and spall damage. For this study, a parametric computer-aided drafting (CAD) environment (17, 18)
141 is used to generate an extruded cross section of the representative tunnel geometry and analyze its
142 intersection with the blast-induced damage spheres (yellow for breach and red for spall), as demonstrated
143 in Figure 2. This approach has also been implemented in Matlab (19), which is more conducive to a
144 parametric study for a range of threat sizes or tunnel geometries.

145 TUNNEL PROTOTYPES

146 To demonstrate the proposed approach, three tunnel geometries are considered as representative
147 examples in the current US tunnel inventory: rectangular, horseshoe, and circular. Each tunnel supports two
148 lanes of traffic moving in the same direction. Lane width and shoulder size vary in all three tunnels. Cross-
149 sectional details and typical threat locations are shown in Figure 3. The cross-sectional openings and wall
150 thicknesses are based on tunnels currently in service in the United States. The horseshoe and circular liner
151 thicknesses are scaled to approximately 22 times the effective diameter of the tunnel opening (based on the

152 cross-sectional area). The rectangular tunnel liner thickness is also based on the effective diameter-opening
153 approach but is further increased to account for the additional bending action. These systems are examined
154 for detonation of an explosive charge within the tunnel at the center of the right lane, as shown in Figure 3.
155 Reduction in pressure demands at the entry/exit and damage to the end portals are not considered.

156 FEMA 426 (20) specifies a range of design values for vehicle threats (ranging from sedans to vans
157 and light cargo trucks) from 500 to 4000 lbs of TNT. Three charge weights of 500, 1000 and 2000 lbs of
158 TNT (labeled A, B and C, respectively) were chosen to conform both to the FEMA hazard scale as well as
159 the charge sizes within the parametric range of damage predictions shown in Table 1 from UFC 3-340-02.
160 These threat sizes are also similar to those selected in previous studies of blast effects in tunnels (11).

161 The evaluation performed in this study conservatively assumes that the charges will be located on
162 the road surface ($B_f = 1.0$) due to the uncertainty of the vehicle size and to avoid the complexities associated
163 with air burst (such as Mach stem and complex reflection). The yellow hemispheres in Figure 4 indicate
164 the charge location in the center of the right lane, consistent with Figure 3. Different vehicle heights and
165 delivery methods can be accounted for by varying the elevation of the explosive. Breached areas are
166 removed from the tunnel geometry, while areas outside the breach radius yet still affected by spalling are
167 represented in red. Road surfaces are shown strictly for clarity – this visualization only considers damage to
168 the tunnel walls. Crater formation at the road surface and blast effects on tunnel lining below the road
169 surface are outside the scope of this study but will be considered in future work.

170 As shown from Figure 4, the circular tunnel exhibits the least damage when exposed to threats A
171 and B, while the rectangular and horseshoe tunnel experienced significant breach when exposed to the same
172 threat levels. A summary of affected areas and threat size for each tunnel is tabulated in Figure 5. Both the
173 rectangular and horseshoe tunnels experience breach at all threat levels as well as a total loss of cross-
174 section for the larger threats – in these cases, a cave-in of the surrounding media due to loss of support
175 would be very likely. Damage cases in which up to half of the cross-section is lost would be candidates for
176 progressive collapse evaluation to prevent further loss of the cross-section. Though all three tunnels have
177 the same throughput, the circular tunnel suffered significantly less liner damage due to a larger standoff
178 distance from the charge via the increased shoulders as shown in Figure 3.

179 **COMPARISON TO COMPUTATIONAL MODELS**

180 To validate the proposed approach, high-fidelity analyses in LS-DYNA (21) were performed with
181 the rectangular tunnel prototype in Figure 3. The explosive threats are assumed to be located on the ground
182 (i.e. as a surface charge) to eliminate the influence of partial reflection (Mach Stem) if the charge were
183 elevated in a vehicle. The blast effects resulting from the surface charge assumption are conservative and
184 produce an upper bound of applied pressure. The Multi-Material Arbitrary Lagrangian Eulerian method is
185 chosen in LS-DYNA to simulate the blast event. Concrete is modeled with Lagrangian solid elements with
186 an approximate discretization dimension of 4 inches. The tunnel liner is modeled with 5 solid elements
187 through its thickness, and about one million total solid elements are used to model a 50-foot length of the
188 tunnel. The outside of the tunnel is approximated as a rigid boundary. This assumption results in a
189 conservative evaluation of damage by ensuring maximum energy will be reflected back into the liner,
190 providing an upper bound for blast damage. In reality, the surrounding media will absorb some of the
191 pressure shock depending on its impedance – though this energy dissipation is neglected in this analysis, it
192 can be considered via a more complex numerical analysis. A real tunnel system will interact with its backfill
193 substrates, potential groundwater, and unstable sediment and/or rock formations. Variation in the
194 surrounding media can affect the response of the liner to blast depending on the longitudinal location of the
195 threat – critical locations could then be identified and prioritized for strengthening.

196 The concrete material behavior is approximated as linear elastic with an elastic modulus of 3600
197 ksi (approximately corresponding to a compressive strength of 4000 psi). Since the damage response is
198 governed by shock wave propagation and associated tensile concrete failure through the liner thickness, the
199 steel reinforcement is neglected in the current analyses. Symmetry about the charge location is used to
200 decrease the computational expense. The explosive charge is modeled with LS-DYNA Material Type 8,
201 *MAT_HIGH_EXPLOSIVE_BURN. The JWL equation of state is used to link the explosive reaction

202 pressure to the air volume elements. Both the charge and air domains are constructed with solid elements.
203 The 500-lb charge is used as a demonstration to compare the proposed approach with the
204 computational analysis. The analysis in LS-DYNA takes approximately 4 hours to analyze 3 milliseconds
205 of the close-in blast (which captures the peak exposure) when performed on a modern desktop computer
206 with i7 quad core processor, 16GB of RAM, and solid state hard drive. Using the same hardware, the
207 proposed approach takes approximately 10 seconds to analyze the same tunnel segment. Figure 6 compares
208 the results of the computational model and the proposed approach. The contour in Figure 6(a) represents
209 an overlay of maximum principle tensile stresses on the interior face of the tunnel liner at various time steps
210 in the analysis. The red shaded areas indicate that the tensile stress has exceeded the concrete tensile
211 capacity (taken as 316 psi). Breach is indicated at regions where the tensile capacity has been reached
212 through the liner thickness during the analysis. Spalled regions have reached the tensile capacity only on
213 the interior face due to thru-thickness shock propagation. Note that more advanced concrete damage models
214 are available, but they were not chosen in this particular study due to their complexity, increased
215 computation time, and limited accessibility to practicing engineers. Rather, a simplified failure criteria that
216 provides an upper bound of concrete damage is used.
217 Figure 6 shows good agreement of the spatial distribution of damage between the LS-DYNA
218 analysis and the proposed approach. The overall areas of spall and breach damage agree within 10%, with
219 the computational model indicating slightly more breach and the proposed approach slightly more spall.
220 This variation is most likely caused by the pressure variability in the computational model due to
221 confinement and reflection of the shock wave – these effects will be considered in future study.

222 PARAMETRIC STUDY

223 Due to its computational efficiency, the proposed approach readily allows for parametric variation
224 of the tunnel geometry and rapid determination of damaged regions for a given threat. In this way, tunnels
225 with non-uniform cross sections and/or cross passageways could be quickly assessed with the same
226 framework. This approach provides two important tools to the designer. First, the area contour of damage
227 can be quantified for a given threat. The damaged zone can then be used as the input for a progressive
228 collapse assessment of the tunnel liner. Second, the approach can be used to examine a range of threats and
229 assess the correlation of increasing damage with increases in blast intensity.

230 Several typical relationships between damage and demand (i.e. breach/spall area versus charge size)
231 are illustrated in Figure 7. In scenario 1, damage increases very quickly at low threat levels but slows down
232 considerably at point A. For this scenario, the system could conceptually be designed for threat intensity A,
233 as larger threats would not significantly increase the damage. Scenarios 2 and 3 have an initial region where
234 damage accumulates slowly with increasing threat size. This could represent a small charge size which
235 would have minimal damage until the spall threshold is reached. Both scenarios 2 and 3 reach a critical
236 point B, at which the gradient decreases and damage starts to increase with small changes in threat size.
237 Then at points C and D, the rate of damage decreases as larger threats become less effective at inflicting
238 additional damage. Point B or points C/D could be used for design depending on the allowable level of
239 damage for the system.

240 This approach is implemented in Figure 8 for the three prototype tunnels. The solid curves in
241 Figure 8 show the relationship between charge weight and damaged area, while the dotted lines represents
242 the gradient or slope of the threat-to-damage relationship. For all the three tunnels, the TNT weight was
243 progressively increased from 200 lbs to 2300 lbs of TNT, which is the maximum value in the valid range
244 of the empirical model in UFC 3-340-02 (see Table 1).

245 The dotted line for the rectangular tunnel in Figure 8(a) shows that the damage gradient initially
246 reduces with increasing blast load, reaching the minimum at approximately 500 lbs and then increasing
247 again at about 900 lbs. After this point, the damage vs. charge relationship most resembles scenario 3 in
248 Figure 7. Point B corresponds to the gradient value just before its minimum. Point D corresponds to the
249 subsequent gradient value after which the tangential slope of the gradient line demonstrably decreases. For
250 the rectangular tunnel, Point D at 900 lbs could be an optimal value for design because the damage increases
251 more significantly for a modest increase in threat size up to this point. This is consistent with the results

252 shown in Figures 4 and 5, which showed significant increases in breach area as the threat is increased from
253 500 to 1000 lbs. The horseshoe and circular tunnels show similar behavior to that of the rectangular tunnel,
254 with a more pronounced change of gradient beyond point D. The critical threat size range in which
255 breaching rapidly increases is approximately 400 - 700 lbs of TNT for the horseshoe tunnel and 1300 - 1500
256 lbs of TNT for the circular tunnel, which are marked in Figure 8(b) and (c) between points B and D. The
257 hazard level at point D could be used to establish the initial conditions for progressive collapse evaluation
258 of the tunnel. Up to this point, enough of the cross-section remains such that an evaluation of the damaged
259 liner to resist subsequent progressive collapse could be warranted and effective. Threat sizes beyond this
260 point will increase the damage such that the cross-section circumference becomes completely breached and
261 a subsequent cave-in becomes likely.

262 To avoid breach, the wall thickness could be increased via shotcrete, additional precast concrete
263 panels, or other means. As a simple illustration in Table 2, the horseshoe and rectangular systems wall
264 thickness can be increased to 3.63 ft and 3.47 ft, respectively, to eliminate the occurrence of breach under
265 the 1000 lbs VBIED, though spalling will still occur. This approach can be extended to any charge size and
266 tunnel geometry to provide the owner with a means to estimate a target level of design performance. As an
267 example, the liner thickness needed to eliminate breaching is plotted for each tunnel geometry for increasing
268 charge size in Figure 9. The results show that for standard VBIED sizes, it is possible to mitigate breach
269 damage via increases in wall thickness.

270 CONCLUSIONS

271 An examination of concrete tunnel liner vulnerability to blast was conducted for three prototype
272 systems subjected to a range of blast load intensities. The tunnels all provide access to two lanes of traffic
273 but have varying geometries that include a rectangular, horseshoe, and circular shape corresponding to three
274 tunnel types currently in service in the U.S. A simplified analysis approach is presented, and numerical
275 modeling is performed as validation. The numerical model was developed to conservatively evaluate the
276 maximum blast damage. The results of the study are as follows:

- 277 1. Empirical equations in UFC 3-340-02 can reasonably predict the upper bound of concrete liner breach
278 and spall damage caused by blast loads. This approach is highly efficient, and the results are comparable
279 to numerical models; however, the approach relies on several conservative assumptions and should be
280 considered as an upper bound for damage prediction.
- 281 2. Three existing tunnels and three charge weights are analyzed. As expected, the results show that the
282 spall and breach damage is correlated to standoff distance for a specific charge weight.
- 283 3. The results also indicate that a moderately sized VBIED can produce a significant amount of breaching
284 in a tunnel system.
- 285 4. The approach can be readily implemented to estimate the amount of liner thickness retrofit needed to
286 mitigate damage under a specific threat.
- 287 5. The approach can also be used to determine the minimum recommended design threats based on the
288 gradient of the threat-to-damage relationship. Inflection points in this relationship can be used to
289 identify hazard levels at which a progressive collapse evaluation would be warranted.

290
291
292 Tunnel damage under blast is a developing topic. A reliable and efficient methodology is needed
293 for engineering design and analysis. Future efforts include improved analytical approaches for increasingly
294 accurate and efficient predictions, as well as coupling the effects of blast with associated hazards such as
295 fire.

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302 AUTHOR CONTRIBUTION STATEMENT

303 The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: all, data
304 collection: all, analysis and interpretation of results: all, and draft manuscript preparation: all. All authors
305 reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

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Figure 2: Spherical damage mapping due to blast in a rectangular tunnel

Rectangular

Horseshoe

Circular

Figure 3: Tunnel geometries and details (all dimensions in feet = 0.3048 m)

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Figure 4: Tunnel spall and breach damage for threats A, B and C

Figure 5: Summary of spall and breach damage experienced by each tunnel type for each blast threat

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Figure 6: Comparison of spall and breach damage contours from (a) computational (LS-DYNA) analysis and (b) the proposed approach for the rectangular tunnel subjected to the 500-lb threat

Figure 7: Typical damage vs charge relation

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Figure 8: Damage area (spall + breach) versus charge weight for each tunnel

Figure 9: Tunnel liner thicknesses needed to prevent breach

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Table 1: Parametric ranges for spall prediction from Tab. 4-15a, UFC 3-340-02 (16)

Parameter	Max.	Min.	Avg.
R , in	360	0.1	21.0
Charge weight, W , lb	2299	0.03	24.4
Case length, in	60.0	0.80	8.8
Case diameter, in	18.0	0.80	4.0
Case thickness, in	0.62	0.00	0.05
$R/W^{1/3}$, in/lb ^{1/3}	12.1	0.008	0.70
Concrete thickness, T , in	84.0	2.00	9.23
f'_c , psi	13815	1535	5067

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Table 2: Tunnel performance and retrofit requirements for the 1000-lb threat				
Tunnel type	Design/Retrofit	Wall Thickness (ft)*	Total Damaged Area (ft ²)*	Breaching Area (ft ²)
Rectangular Tunnel	Design	1.75	3155	1857
	Retrofit	3.47	837	0
Horseshoe Tunnel	Design	1.50	3689	2770
	Retrofit	3.64	467	0
Circular Tunnel	Design	2.06	1277	373
	Retrofit	2.90	534	0
* 1 ft = 0.3048 m, 1ft ² = 0.092 m ²				

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